

HIGH SPEED NETWORKING OF FUTURE MILSATCOM

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ABSTRACT: Future high speed networking of highly mobile forces will be a major requirement to fully leverage information technologies to support warfighting capabilities. This paper presents a vision of the impact of advanced C3I technologies on future defense operations. The complementary characteristics of fiber optics, terrestrial RF, and satellite communications systems can be exploited to achieve a militarily responsive high speed "global grid" communications infrastructure. Some of the salient technical challenges facing transparent incorporation of high speed satellite communications into such an architecture are briefly discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

The technical, economic and sociopolitical debate over the relative advantages of satellite communications versus fiber optic communications has been ongoing for some time now (see, for example, *Conference Proceedings, Fibersat 86*; and Coddling, 1990). The debate is not yet completed and key data are still being elucidated. The ultimate outcome of this competition might be a clear dominance of one technology over the other, but it is likely that both media will be important components of our future global communications network.

The primary reason for this hybrid solution lies in the unique characteristics of the respective media, which are summarized in Table 1. In particular, the growing importance of, and requirements for, reliable, reasonably high capacity communications to mobile platforms clearly mandates RF channels in the network architecture. Satellite communications (SATCOM) offer the unique advantages of reliable service to ships and aircraft operating at great distances from terrestrial RF networks (which must be line-of-sight to utilize frequencies suitable for moderate capacity communications).

The defense community is intently addressing the issue of SATCOM versus fiber optic communications. It is logical to expect that the dependence on SATCOM, measured as the ratio of aggregate SATCOM capacity to total SATCOM plus fiber capacity, will be greater for the defense sector than the analogous fractional dependency for the commercial sector. The reasons are quite straightforward and obvious. Whereas the bulk of commercial communications links will be established between fixed locations, the fundamental mission of the military -- to deploy anywhere in the world, create its own organic infrastructure for highly mobile command and control, and fight to defend our national interests -- clearly requires heavy dependence on RF networking. Furthermore, recently evolved defense doctrine, which emphasizes reduced force structures and a CONUS-based military, requires the ability for rapid

deployments under crisis response timelines to provide global power projection. Reductions in personnel and weapon system procurements will require even greater leveraging of information technologies to ensure the ability of U.S. forces to fight and win under diverse conflict scenarios. Satellite communications are uniquely suited to provide the intra-theater instant infrastructure for C3I requirements, as well as the long-haul connectivity between the deployed forces and senior leadership in the U.S. and CONUS-based logistical and intelligence support networks.

Together with the commercial sector, the defense community will exploit the advantageous characteristics of future high data rate fiber optic communications systems. The ability of emerging fiber standards and protocols such as Switched Multimegabit Data System (SMDS), Synchronous Optical Network (SONET) and Asynchronous Transfer Mode (ATM) to provide high rate multimedia services to a large population of users in a massive, heterogeneous network will be realized -- probably within the next 15 years. This futuristic fiber network is sometimes referred as the "crystal grid."

Given the desired attributes that fiber-based systems offer, but recognizing their inherent limitations, leads to considerations of systems that have complementary characteristics but are nonetheless highly interoperable with fiber systems. This paper briefly examines the major issues associated with augmenting the terrestrial crystal grid with satellite communications to achieve a balanced, responsive system for defense networking over the coming decades. It should be noted that due to the far-term horizons and somewhat speculative nature of most of the following discussion, the views presented here are those of the authors alone and do not necessarily represent an official position by any Government agency or organization. Nevertheless, many of the concepts discussed here are essentially consistent with other "official visions" (see, for example, *STAR 21: Strategic Technologies for the Army of the 21st Century*).

II. DEFENSE APPLICATIONS OF HIGH SPEED SATELLITE NETWORKS

Ongoing developments in the commercial sector will eventually establish worldwide broadband fiber optic connectivity between major switching centers. Thus, long-haul high capacity fiber and new high speed switching technologies will replace the mix of copper cables, terrestrial microwave and satellite links that today provide links among major trunking centers. This terrestrial fiber network will be extended beyond the high speed switching centers using MANs and LANs to ultimately reach fixed-site

Table 1

TRANSMISSION MEDIA CHARACTERISTICS

Medium	Advantages	Limitations
Fiber Optic Communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enormous bandwidths - Extremely low bit error rates - Minimum time delay between two points 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Physically vulnerable to natural or intentional damage - Cannot service mobile users, to include ground mobile people and vehicles, ships, and aircraft
SATCOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simultaneous direct broadcast provides service over enormous geographical areas - Mobile user networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cannot (generally) repair on-orbit [may change over the next 10 to 20 yrs] - Finite spectrum available - Noise and interference susceptible - Fixed time delay of at least .25 sec for geosynchronous satellites
Terrestrial RF Network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile user networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited service area - Many repeaters required - Finite spectrum available - Noise and interference susceptible

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users (homes, office buildings, factories, etc.). Undoubtedly, the crystal grid will be augmented with other access modes, such as cellular telephone systems, to provide a gateway (at least at low to moderate data rates) for worldwide accessibility for mobile customers. True high data rate, or high burst rate, services are expected to grow dramatically in the coming decades, so that future public networks will not merely transmit multiplexed trunks comprised of many low rate services. Indeed, the future public network will statistically multiplex many different classes of service.

The defense community will leverage this extensive network to provide worldwide connectivity between fixed installations, i.e., major headquarters and centers. Multilevel security technologies will facilitate transmission of sensitive defense information (intelligence data, operational traffic, logistical data, computer-computer communications etc.) over high speed public networks. Use of the public network to satisfy defense requirements for high capacity, worldwide communications will probably be the most economical means of interconnectivity under non-stressing environments. However, this least-cost solution has serious deficiencies when the military is required to operate under conditions of international crisis or open warfare.

Although the actual message traffic can be adequately protected by encryption techniques, routing information contained in frame headers must remain un-encrypted for switching in the public network. Thus, an adversary could gain useful data by analyzing the time dependent traffic flow between military organizations. There are techniques to partially alleviate this problem but they require specific features to be designed into an international system in order to satisfy U.S. military requirements. Furthermore, the very nature of an international public network implies that foreign governments can not only derive information from the system, but may also be able to control, or at least influence, its operation.

Since military operations are highly mobile, use of standard public access ports through cellular phone systems might be contemplated, but again, the inherent vulnerabilities of such systems to jamming and interference make them inadequate for military uses. Additionally, cellular systems may not be available in isolated regions where the military must operate. Finally, the physical medium supporting the fiber communications channel is itself highly vulnerable to sabotage or disruption; indeed, susceptibility to damage makes it prudent to maintain alternative long-haul capabilities for civil communications in the event of natural disasters.

The limitations noted above for defense utilization of the "crystal grid" can be largely alleviated by employing complementary systems based on terrestrial and satellite RF networks. To provide an instant infrastructure for command and control communications anywhere in the world during crisis response deployments, the "crystal grid" terrestrial backbone must be supplemented by a worldwide satellite network. Satellites can simultaneously provide both intra-theater, non-line-of-sight connectivity as well as long-haul connectivity of first echelon forces with CONUS headquarters and support bases. The robust backbone system comprised of terrestrial fiber optic links and a complementary satellite network will provide a militarily responsive "global grid" network. As the theater of operations is built-up, local intra-theater augmentations of the backbone "global grid" will occur as terrestrial RF networks are put in place to enhance capacity for mobile subscribers.

The salient defense requirements for mobile connectivity to aircraft, ships, and ground mobile vehicular and man-pack systems exists today, but explosive developments in information technologies will create tremendous pressure for ever-greater capacity in mobile networks. To some extent, these developments parallel innovations in commercial services, which promise high performance personalized information processing and communications systems to empower the "active individual" of the

future. Such personalized "info-centers" may include services such as PC-based videoteleconferencing and voice operated workstation capability with prodigious resident processing power ("microsupercomputers") as well as direct networked access to enormous data bases and information processing centers. But, again, network connectivity for such mobile civilian nodes will likely be handled by broadband RF cellular architectures which locally tie the user back into the "crystal grid" ("an antenna on every lamppost"). Many of the commercially developed information services for the "active individual" can be adapted for defense applications, but unique requirements for military communications will necessitate RF networks that are not only broadband, but that also possess properties of AJ and LPI/LPD, and can be securely accessed from remote and hostile environments.

The emerging developments in information processing and networking portend radical paradigm shifts in the conduct of military operations. The tactical commander of the future will have personal tools (akin to technologies for the "active individual") and organizational tools which will dramatically enhance the speed, fidelity, resolution and flexibility of command and control (C2). For example, detailed status information on each individual (vital signs, injuries, level of fatigue, equipment status, etc.) and each weapon system (fuel remaining, damaged or inoperative subsystems, number of rounds remaining, etc.) can be monitored and distributed as needed throughout the network (for example, to command operations center, medical center, logistics and maintenance support center, etc.). High speed networking will also support uniquely military requirements for telerobotic command and control, "virtual staffs" comprised of software surrogates to support even fairly low echelon commanders, and advanced interactive model-based distributed simulations for battle preparation and training. The amalgamation and synthesis of this vast array of information will produce a "super-reality" view of the battlefield, facilitating a dynamically adaptive order of battle and operation plan. Planning and coordination at an incredibly fine-grained resolution, coupled with real-time analysis of the exigent uncertainties of the military environment, will enable operations to be tailored in real-time and executed in a near-optimal manner.

Future capabilities will likely be so powerful that "force-fitting" them onto the template of traditional military C2 will limit their potential. Rather, it is likely that the prodigious impact of information technologies will engender significant advancements in the paradigms that have characterized the management and conduct of warfare since the days of Napoleon (General and small unit staff structures, linearity of the battlefield, etc.) Dispersed, distributed information processing and decisionmaking will facilitate cooperative engagements on a scale that spans the full battlespace -- on land, at sea, and in the air -- all with a level of speed and complexity almost unimaginable by today's standards. Such capabilities will result from the fusion of vast quantities of information on friendly and enemy status, and -- most importantly -- the real-time distribution of meaningful processed information to the right commander or weapon system at the decisive point in time and space.

To prevent "info-gridlock," only relevant information in the required format must be presented to each commander or weapon system on the battlefield. Such information may be loosely categorized into three classes: specific domain information for a given entity such as identification and location of a target to be engaged by a particular weapon system; regional domain information for all elements in an area of operations, such as weather, terrain, and enemy activity in their area of influence or region of interest; and low priority general information. A constant flow of information will occur throughout the battlespace and will consist of two general modes. Specific domain information will be principally routed through terrestrial RF links using local area broadband high net throughput protocols in a stochastic cellular architecture. Such an architecture could support broadband "nearest

neighbor" traffic flows (a dispersed systolic processing approach) in which each element of the network can be considered to be the hub of its own cellular region, with each hub moving in a stochastic fashion with respect to other hubs. (This type of network may be analogous to some proposals for networking cars on the intelligent vehicular highway systems of the future.) It is quite possible that technology advancements will enable a single intelligent, adaptive, multi-band multi-waveform radio node that can communicate over various modes (satellite, LOS, skywave, etc.) with moderate data rates (~100 KBps) from mobile terminals. (DoD's Speakeasy Program is already working toward this goal.)

Regional domain information and general information inherently involve point-multipoint distribution topologies and may best be handled via satellite communications. Such wide area direct broadcast service will avoid congestion created within the terrestrial RF cellular network if it attempts to disseminate the same information to all elements of the network. Examples of information products that require multipoint distribution include intelligence products from data fusion centers; over-the-air-rekeying (OTAR); "super maps" (a full intelligence preparation of the battle zone including geographical, topographical, weather, terrain, friendly/enemy status, etc.); and general news and information services.

Satellite-based communications can provide several other unique services to the air-land-sea battlespace network. During initial build-up of the theater area of operations, the satellite backbone will provide both local and long-haul network connectivity until the terrestrial RF network infrastructure is established. Additionally, satellites are uniquely capable of providing nearly instantaneous access to all key intelligence, logistical and operational data base networks within CONUS. Thus, the tactical commander of the future will have at his or her immediate disposal the vast resources of CONUS-based fiber-connected information and supercomputer systems, regardless of where that commander's region of operations is. SATCOM can make this information accessibility virtually transparent to the operational units; indeed, the promise of software surrogates (sometimes referred to as "information agents" or "Knowbots") implies that locating, evaluating, and processing information within the CONUS "information arsenal" may be performed by nearly autonomous software entities that understand the information requirements of their master and can maneuver through the information jungle to extract what is needed and present it in the desired format. Such software entities may actually be capable of "forward-thinking" for contingencies, such as independently preparing detailed maps of several nearby cities that the commander might be fighting in within the next few days. A further unique ability of SATCOM is to network independent "islands of conflict" on the nonlinear battlefield by extending communication links outward from a friendly enclave which is completely surrounded by the enemy.

The implications of this futuristic scenario are tremendous, ranging from greatly enhanced "tooth-to-tail" ratios of combat

commands to greatly streamlined force structures which nonetheless can project decisive U.S. combat power anywhere in the world. The technologies to realize such futuristic capabilities, and to implement them affordably, will be developed over the next 10 to 25 years. A key element of this overall architecture will be very high data rate networks with virtually transparent interfaces between fiber optic systems, terrestrial RF networks, and satellite communication networks. The issues and technical challenges to achieve these lofty goals are just now beginning to receive widespread attention. In the next section, we examine some of the key challenges for the transparent, optimally organized integration of fiber optics and satellite-based networks.

III. TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The design of a communication system seeks to optimize certain defining parameters of the system given the characteristics of the transmission medium and other systemic constraints. Given the very wide disparity in the physical properties (signal attenuation and scattering, random noise processes and associated data error statistics, signal propagation speed and associated delays for total channel path length, etc.) of the medias for fiber optic and satellite communications, integrating SATCOM and fiber networks is certainly a non-trivial problem. The waveforms, protocols, data formats, switching technologies and other standards that are developed for fiber communications may not be optimal or even suitable for SATCOM implementation and vice versa. This section will highlight some of the technical issues that must be addressed to effectively integrate satellites and terrestrial fiber optic networks in an optimally efficient and user transparent manner. A fundamental question that will require significant analysis is: Should SATCOM be considered essentially as a long "fiber optic cable," should satellites operate as another ATM switch in the network, or are other (less straightforward) implementations more suitable? The issues that we briefly discuss below include latency and delays, bandwidth, data rates and associated error statistics, packet protocols and associated switching technology, and considerations for statistically multiplexing significantly different classes of service (voice, computer-computer, video, etc.) that each has its own associated quality of service requirements. Table 2 presents a simplified, high-level comparison of major technical parameters of SATCOM and fibercom systems today.

Wideband SATCOM systems today may have aggregate bandwidths (BWs) approaching 1 GHz, but currently flying satellites typically break this total up over a number of distinct transponders. Soon-to-fly technology, such as that incorporated in NASA's ACTS satellite, will facilitate single transponder BWs of about 1 GHz. A key area for technology advancement will be in miniaturization of the terrestrial terminals for wideband systems. Such terminals today are quite large, and at best can be considered transportable if they are not fully fixed-site installations. Thus, if high speed satellite networks are to provide global grid access for mobile military platforms, the terminals and antenna systems

Table 2

Simplified Comparison of Fundamental Parameters

NOTE: This table denotes a "typical value of the parameter with today's technology"/"estimate of parameter's value 10 - 20 years into the future".

Parameter	SATCOM	Fiber
Carrier Freq, fo	~ 10 ¹⁰ Hz/10 ¹¹ Hz	~ 10 ¹⁴ Hz
Typical Bandwidth (Typical Max Data Rate)	~ 10 MHz/1 GHz	~ 1 GHz/~ 1 THz
Trans-Atlantic Propagation Delay	250 ms (assumes geostationary satellite)	< ~ 50 ms
Bit-Error-Rates	10 ⁻⁶ /10 ⁻¹²	~ 10 ⁻¹⁵
Multiplexing Techniques (including packet segmentation)	FDM, FDMA, TDM, TDMA, CDMA/ DAMA-TDMA, DAMA-FDMA, SDMA	WDM SONET/ATM

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require significant miniaturization.

Given the frequency, BW, associated data rate, beamwidth/coverage area and maximum tolerable BER, the major engineering trade parameters for design of a satellite link are the transmitter EIRP (a power-aperture measure), receiver G/T, modulation and coding schemes and symbol detection/decision algorithms. The EIRP, G/T, and beamwidth parameters all scale as the area of the antenna aperture and thus small mobile antennas will probably require greater transmitter powers, quieter receivers (although technology is already pushing theoretical limits at lower MILSATCOM frequencies), and greater coding overhead.

Of course, trades can be made between the satellite and terminal design parameters. If one is willing to develop (and pay for!) a large spacecraft, terminals could be significantly reduced in size. Alternatively, a "hub-spoke" architecture could be utilized in which small "disadvantaged" terminals communicate with a large central "hub" station through a modest-sized satellite; this concept supports current very small aperture terminal (VSAT) architectures. The penalty in this case is the large central hub, and a further drawback may be limitations on data rates.

Technology advancement may facilitate quite large yet affordable communications satellites in the future. Large high efficiency active aperture arrays will likely be achieved over the next few decades with individual active elements affordably mass produced as monolithic 3-D electronics packages. Such an array could be compactly stowed for launch and subsequently deployed on orbit. Techniques to auto-cohere the array without stringent structural requirements could reduce spacecraft weight and hence launch costs. A very large active aperture array can be used to create multiple high gain beams that can be rapidly steered by virtue of electronic agility of the beams. In principle, two large arrays (one receive, one transmit) could be used to produce multiple simultaneous beams and, hence, to network a number of users in a variety of ways.

Communications at very high data rates to small portable/mobile terminals may require many decades of technological advancements to achieve, if indeed it can be done. New concepts may be required. As an example, for scenarios where there are many mobile users in a region, a cooperative distributed ensemble of receivers may provide a solution to the problem of error correction without incurring very high latency penalties. If (uncorrectable but detectable) bit errors occur on the downlink, the dispersed set of receivers may not all have the same elements of the bit stream corrupted, so that queries from a receiver which detects an error (which can not be corrected by an FEC or other algorithm) to its neighboring receivers (linked via the terrestrial RF network) can facilitate comparison of received data and local (e.g., via terrestrial network) correction of corrupted data. Of course, use of long constraint length codes will no doubt be used in the SATCOM system, so in reality blocks of corrupted data would be identified and corrected by sharing information amongst the dispersed receivers. Clearly, detailed calculations will be required here to fully understand the nature of the error statistics and their space-time correlations (i.e., over the ensemble of receivers), as well as the issues of latency and potential congestion on the terrestrial RF network as it attempts to serve as a policeman to correct downlink errors. At some point, this error detection/correction scheme breaks down, viz, when the error occurs on the uplink or onboard the satellite before transmission. The terrestrial network must have the requisite distributed intelligence to determine when this condition has probably occurred, and then the only recourse may be to go back over the satellite link to request re-transmission. If this request is routed back to the terrestrial origination site, the fastest that corrected information would be received by the mobile user is ~ 750 msec after original transmission, which is a grossly high latency period. This delay could be cut to ~500 msec if the satellite had sufficient buffer memory capacity (and of course if the data in that

memory was verified to be uncorrupted). For some classes of service, even this may be an unacceptably long latency period.

Future high performance processors, perhaps implementing neural network architectures or of "fuzzy logic" codes, may be sufficiently powerful to limit the number of requests for re-transmitted information by "inferring" the correct data stream from "semantic content" of larger slices of the sequence. Also, for some classes of service, it may suffice to inhibit the re-transmission of lost or corrupted cells. For example, voice conversations are, relatively speaking, highly robust against sporadic interference, since the human brain is constantly examining semantic structure and content, and people will naturally interrogate the other party if their message is unclear. Unfortunately, as data compression schemes become more powerful and more widely utilized, each transmitted bit inherently carries "more information" and, hence, even very low fractional losses might be intolerable and non-recoverable.

A major distinction exists between emerging techniques for multiplexing diverse classes of service on high speed fiber networks, and traditional multiplexing/multiple access schemes for satellites. SATCOM systems generally operate on a circuit connectivity basis in which a dedicated channel links two or more users for the duration of a communications session, if not indeed for a protracted period of dedicated service. Multiplexing of signals generally involves frequency division or time division multiplexing (FDM or TDM) of baseband channels into a group (for example, a telephone trunk line) and the composite signal is then relayed via the satellite. Most satellites to date have essentially operated as relays without on-board switching, and in some cases the received uplink signal may simply be shifted in frequency before being transmitted back to earth, without any demodulation and regenerative signal processing. Satellites have been designed and operated for both analog and digital communications, with more recent satellites favoring digital systems.

In addition to multiplexing at baseband, satellite systems may also offer multiple access services in which a transponder is "shared" among a group of users according to some access protocol. Typical multiple access protocols include frequency division multiple access (FDMA), time division multiple access (TDMA), and code division multiple access (CDMA) in which spread spectrum techniques are employed to facilitate multiple orthogonal waveforms. Network control for these various protocols is also required, and recent emphasis has focused on demand assigned multiple access (DAMA) for network control of MILSATCOM services. All of these multiple access schemes are circuit oriented, i.e., connectivity between subscribers is established and maintained during the course of their entire communications session.

This *modus operandi* for current and past SATCOM differs greatly from emerging techniques and standard for fiber-optic communications. High data rate fiber systems will employ statistical multiplexing of widely different classes of service using fast-packet switching techniques. Data streams from multiple input ports are segmented, and the individual cells are transported through the network as SONET frames. Fast-packet switching generally does not involve examination of the frame contents at each switching node to verify data integrity. Instead, the destination terminal determines the quality of the received cells and requests retransmissions for frames that were lost or suffered corruption.

Considerable work needs to be done to understand the best use of satellites in high speed networks. A central networking issue centers on whether SATCOM should continue to provide circuit-oriented services, or migrate to virtual circuit operation which would be more akin to fast-packet networks using SONET/ATM protocols. To conduct virtual circuit operations over a satellite will require significant technology advancements, although it undoubtedly can be done at some (modest) data rates. However, such an operational concept presupposes that the satellite demodulates the uplink(s) and

performs fast-packet switching on the data frames to route them to appropriate downlink beams. The electronic agility of the active aperture arrays would be required to be orders of magnitude faster than today's capabilities to make such a scheme work at high frame rates.

If satellites are not used as fast switches, then either they will be used on a switched circuit basis or as "slow" switches (i.e., they must receive relatively long frames or multiple consecutive SONET frames that have the same downlink beam destination). Both technology readiness and mission requirements will contribute to the resolution of this issue. Suffice it to say that for high data rate multi-point distribution, or direct broadcast functions, a circuit switched (or even the current transponding function approach) would probably be acceptable from the perspective of mission requirements and would most certainly be technically feasible. It remains to be seen if statistical multiplexing gains (or perhaps fast DAMA/TDMA or even statistical burst multiple access schemes) will be technically feasible and operationally useful. The unavoidable complexities of long delay intervals, coding overhead to counter interference or (worse yet) jamming, and the likely upper bound of at most a few tens of Gbps data rates may obviate the straightforward approach of operating a satellite as "just another ATM switch" in a fiber-optic network using SONET/ATM protocols. With the advent of WDM and other technologies to exploit the enormous bandwidth potential of optical carriers, data rates on fiber systems are capable of speeds on the order of 1 TBps, which will be several orders of magnitude faster than our most optimistic expectations for satellite systems with very large earth terminals. Thus, ultimately, we will face a tremendous data rate mismatch based on physics, and there may be little sense in developing SONET transparent satellite systems that will be limited to rates of order OC-48. Perhaps, someday, optical carriers with high speed modulation might be devised to communicate from earth to satellites, with relatively low atmospheric losses. Today's notional laser SATCOM systems are very low data rate, and weather penetration may not be achievable; thus such high speed links are speculative today, at best.

The symmetry of information flow within the satellite network itself must also be addressed. Asymmetrical traffic patterns may significantly impact the design of the high speed SATCOM network. For example, data flowing to mobile units may be required to flow ~ 100 MBps, whereas traffic flow from such units may only require at ~ 100 KBps. The network architecture would likely be considerably different for symmetrical vs. asymmetric data flow.

Timing and synchronization issues will become ever more demanding and complex for high speed SATCOM networks, particularly if fast-packet switching is implemented with successive packets being routed over different antenna beams to (or from) subscribers with significantly different line-of-sight distances to the satellite. Current DAMA/TDMA concepts allow compensation for such differential delays, but the precision required for compensation of high speed links becomes more challenging. To illustrate this, consider two users with a differential delay $t \sim 1$ microsecond. If a packet transmitted by User 1 at t_1 arrives at the satellite at T_1 , then User 2 would transmit at $(t_1 + \Delta - t)$ for that packet to arrive at the spacecraft immediately behind packet 1 (where Δ is the packet duration and the sign convention assumes that User 2 is further from the satellite than User 1). Let us suppose that timing and synchronization accuracies must be of order 1 percent of Δ . For packets of ~ 100 bits at rates ~ 10 KBps, $\Delta \sim 10$ milliseconds, whereas for similar length packets at speeds of 100 MBps, $\Delta \sim 1$ microsecond. Corresponding synchronization requirements are ~ 100 microsecond and 10 nanosecond, respectively. For the slow speed case, this timing requirement is of the order of the differential delay between Users 1 and 2, whereas it is four orders of magnitude lower than this for the fast packet case. The point is that extremely precise synchronization will have to exist throughout the high speed SATCOM network if fast packets are

to be used without collision of frames sent by widely separated users. Though there are ways to achieve such synchronization, it is another system complexity (and cost) if high speed frames are to be efficiently routed in a fast DAMA/TDMA fashion over satellites without wastefully large temporal guard bands.

A final issue to note concerns the selection of efficient modulation and coding schemes, as well as transmission security (TRANSEC). SATCOM systems today employ fractional bandwidths that are generally less than 5 percent. If OC-48 rates were to be transmitted over a military EHF link, the fractional bandwidth on the downlink would be ~ 10 percent. Furthermore, this assumes no coding (for error detection/correction) and no TRANSEC (such as direct sequence spread spectrum or frequency hopping), whereas real military systems will require such measures for anti-jam and low probability of intercept and detection. Additionally, capacity is generally decreased significantly in the presence of jamming as a trade-off to maintain some throughput despite the electronic countermeasure. It is not clear with today's technologies how a very wideband signal can be communicated in a heavily jammed environment.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This short paper has not been intended to answer questions or solve problems associated with integrating the "crystal grid" and SATCOM to yield a military responsive "global grid" network. Instead, the purpose here has been to articulate a rational basis for this integration from the perspective of technological potentiality and future prospects for high speed networks to support defense needs and military operations. We have also attempted to identify some of the more salient technical issues and problems associated with developing high speed satellite networks. Much work needs to be done to fully understand this complex problem and to arrive at future solutions which are technically feasible and, perhaps more importantly, affordable.

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